

TECHNICAL AND SECURITY ASPECTS of the CoreTrustSeal Application

Past work of the **CESSDA Trust Working Group*** has identified that technical and security infrastructure elements are a challenge for repositories undertaking self-assessments against the CoreTrustSeal perhaps because staff undertaking self-assessments are usually from the curation rather than the technical side of the organisation. The CoreTrustSeal addresses the issues of technical and security infrastructure through *Requirements 15 and 16*, however, technology and security aspects come into the picture throughout the 16 requirements.

0. BACKGROUND/CONTEXT

- Definition of the designated community (their technical expertise implies type of data formats).
- Outsourcing (technical interoperability, SLAs, certificates)

ORGANIZATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE

I. Mission/Scope

- Should cover people, processes, technology.

II. Licenses

- Types of access, e.g. based on data sensitivity (Authentication/Authorization. Safe room environments in place?)

III. Continuity of Access

- Business continuity of preservation and access functions (Question of technical handover).

IV. Confidentiality/Ethics

- Data with disclosure risk (Appropriate storage? Importance of documented procedures!).

V. Organizational Infrastructure

- Sufficient technical resources?
- Skilled and competent technical staff? Their on-going training?

VI. Expert Guidance

- Access to objective technical expert advice beyond own skilled staff? How is keeping up with new technologies ensured?

DIGITAL OBJECT MANAGEMENT

VII. Data Integrity and Authenticity

- What data and metadata management system is in use? Who has access?

VIII. Appraisal

- Question of dealing with data deposited in non-preferred formats: Do you transform formats? With what software? How do you document changes to files and how do you preserve their significant properties?

IX. Documented Storage Procedures

- Documented processes and procedures, including levels of security, risk management techniques, checks of data files etc.
 - How is the deterioration of storage media handled?

X. Preservation Plan

- Ensure that changes to data technology and user requirements are handled in a stable and timely manner.

XI. Data Quality

- Question of assessing big or complex data.
- Quality checks of documentation and metadata.

XII. Workflows

- Levels of security at each step of the workflow + technical workflows.

XIII. Data Discovery and Identification

- Give advice on technical solutions to enhance usability.
- Technical aspects of data discovery and identification for man and machine.
- Extended searchability of the catalogue (elastic) + metadata harvesting.

XIV. Data Reuse

- Designated community uses technology that implies data formats for access.

Core TDR Technology

TECHNOLOGY

XV. TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

XVI. SECURITY

* **CESSDA ERIC** provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. Its key principle is that Service Providers must be trusted by each other and by their stakeholders. The **CESSDA Trust Working Group** supports this goal through supporting SP's towards certification against the CoreTrustSeal.